

Combating gender stereotypes by highlighting women's contribution to the history of societies

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HerStory Pilot Implementation

HerStory map excursion guidelines for Athens (Greece)

WP2 D2.2

HerStory Consortium

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1. Introduction

The current document is developed to provide guidelines on tour excursion development, for monuments of women in local history and to ensure that the experience is educational, engaging, and respectful, a set of best approaches is presented below, to select the most suitable for each country.

The first phase of excursion will take place in a pilot phase with 160 persons in total (at least in the pilot excursion), so **20 people from each country**, and at least half of the total **(10) must be Young people**. Following to the excursion, all partners will collect the feedback, make the necessary changes, and then prepare another excursion, the final one.

Final excursion will involve 160 persons in total (at least in the excursion), so **20 people from each country**, and at least half of the total **(10) must be Young people**. At the end a total of 320 participants (as a minimum), at least half of the total (160) must be young people.

The participants of the excursions will consist of young people and educators, trainers and academics:

- young people, boys, and girls
- young people active in local community groups such as Municipalities' Youth Councils
- students from the fields of History
- students from the fields of Gender Studies
- youth experts
- youth organizations
- Academics from the fields of History and Gender Studies
- Teachers and educators
- Teachers, and women and human rights organizations experts/activists

Each partner will create different and specific activities for the excursions organized in their city, for the pilots and the final ones. A set of general guidelines are presented below and each partner will analyze and formulate the topics of the guidelines with additions in the excursion descriptions, based on each country specifics.

The target audience for the tour guide guidelines is:

- A. touristic offices and educators.
- B. Small groups (independent excursions)

2. Guidelines to develop a physical excursion

LEVEL 1: How to create a unique tour.

- Define Objectives:

Clearly outline the objectives of the tour. Determine whether it's aimed educational purpose, women's empowerment, cultural understanding, other or a combination of the previously mentioned and provide a small paragraph stating this.

General Objective:

This tour aims to promote cultural understanding and women's empowerment by bringing attention to the significant yet often overlooked roles women have played in the history of Vilnius and Lithuania.

Specific Objectives:

1. To conduct a city tour that visits locations representing the contributions of women who have significantly impacted Lithuanian history.
2. To create a treasure hunt itinerary, allowing different groups to undertake the tour simultaneously with smaller participant numbers.
3. To foster collaboration among tour participants.
4. To promote cultural interest in learning about the notable women of Vilnius.
5. To reevaluate and bring attention to the forgotten deeds of these women.
6. To evaluate the effectiveness of the activity through recorded observations.

- Define the thematic of the excursion:

Organize the specific themes of the tour, according to the objectives, to add depth and structure to the tour experience. Some recommended themes are specific historical periods, specific professions, social activation or general achievements.

The tour will focus on women of Vilnius and Lithuania in the 20th century who challenged societal norms, advanced science, promoted culture, advocated for women's rights, and supported the less fortunate, often under tough historical circumstances such as wars, uprisings and occupations. Many of these women had to choose to do the right thing despite these challenges. Participants will learn about pioneers who broke gender barriers, female innovators, cultural figures in music and literature, and activists who fought for equality. This thematic

approach provides a structured and engaging experience, showcasing the diverse and significant contributions of these remarkable women to local history.

- **Recommend a rich educational content for each woman presented:**

Develop detailed and accurate information about each monument and collect information about historical facts, achievements, and contributions of the women they represent. Include, unique stories, anecdotes and facts that can make the tour engaging and informative. Create compelling stories with the content. Furthermore, you can collaborate with local historians, experts, or women's groups to gain insights into the history and context of the monuments. Moreover, formulate the content and the visual elements of the tour, at a relevant tone of voice.

All detailed information is presented below.

- **Define a compelling excursion tour content:**

Develop the content for the tour excursion, that includes detailed information about each monument and the women they represent, while creating a fascinating and educational experience for the participants. Use multimedia elements if possible.

Additional visual materials will be used during the 1 hr. prepared tour:

1. **Adelė Dirsytė (1909–1955 m.), Photo Source: Wikipedia**

2. Žemaitė Julija Beniuševičiūtė-Žymantienė (1845–1921 m.), Photo source: National Museum of Lithuania, Epaveldas.lt

3. Beatričė Grincevičiūtė (1911–1988 m.), Photo source: B. Grincevičiūtė memorial apartment-museum Beatričės House

4. Felicija Bortkevičienė (1873–1945 m.), Photo source: Maironis Lithuanian Literature Museum

5. Eliza Orzeszkowa (1841–1910 m.), Photo source: National Library of Poland

6. Signatories, Photo source: photo by Aleksandra Jurašaitytė-Vailokaitienė, Lithuanian National Museum

- **Define a compelling excursion tour content:**

Organise the tour excursion, considering factors such chronological order, and geographical proximity of the monuments. Ensure that the route is logistically feasible and allows for a comfortable pace. In case of a big distance among monuments, create different option of tours by organizing specific spot visits, according to chronological order, geographical proximity or specific themes.

Starting/meeting point will be: Lukiškių square, because of its central location, easy access with a public transport and simple recognition.

The 1h tour itinerary:

Meeting point: Lukiškės sq.

1. Aukų st. 2a , Entrance to Museum of Occupations and Freedom Fights
2. Žemaitės square
3. B. Grincevičiūtė Memorial Apartment – Museum (A. Vienuolio str. 12)
4. Gedimino Av. no. 13

5. Kudirka square

Ending point: On the opposite side of the Gedimino av. 12.

Before the tour: To complete the treasure hunt tasks, tour participants must have mobile data and phone/tablet. Participants should be able to watch videos, listen to songs on these devices. Since the activity will be conducted as a team activity, it would be best if at least 1 person in each team would have enough mobile data. Map app will be useful as well. Paper maps can be used too. Free printed city maps are available at tourist information center (Pilies str. 7)

Following instructions for the team leader/guide will be included in table below:

City, Country: Vilnius, Lithuania		
Number	Tour Point	Woman
0 (Meeting point)	Lukiškių sq.	Introduction
<p><i>Introduction to the participants:</i></p> <p>Today we will discover the stories of women who shaped the history of Vilnius and Lithuania. For many years, women's achievements were sadly downplayed and disregarded, but today we talk more about the important work they did. You might have heard about some of these women already; some names will be new to you. By the end of the tour, we hope you will see that for a community to be successful, both men and women need to work together to achieve success.</p> <p>During this walk, you will need to find significant places on Gediminas Avenue that are connected to important women from the past. You will need to answer questions, complete tasks, and share your insights about what you discover.</p> <p>To make it easier (or harder) let us split the group into smaller teams of 3-4 people. One of the participants of each team must have enough mobile data to watch videos.</p> <p><i>Notes for the team leader/guide:</i></p> <p><i>Help participants to split into smaller teams. Preferably mixed groups with both boys/men, girls/women and others in a team. Make sure at least one participant has mobile data to use for tasks.</i></p>		

Before going to the next location ask participants:

Look around. Which of the buildings surrounding Lukiškės Square was a secret KGB prison where hundreds of political prisoners were imprisoned and tortured?

If participants are struggling, ask where the Museum of Occupations and Freedom Fights is located. If they are still struggling, ask to use online maps.

1	Aukų str. 2A Entrance to Museum of Occupations and Freedom Fights	Adelė Dirsytė (1909-1955)
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Text to say about this famous woman:

Adele was much like many other women who helped to shape Lithuania's first Republic. She worked in various youth and women's organizations, wrote articles, poetry, and organized seminars. Adele also taught German at a girls' school until her arrest by KGB in 1946 for "contra-revolutionary" activities. Despite enduring eight months of torture in a secret KGB prison, her spirit remained unbroken. Even in Siberian gulags she continued teaching and supporting other women, emphasizing forgiveness over revenge. This message was captured in a small prayer book called "Mary, Save Us,". Translated into more than nine languages and distributed in hundreds of thousands of copies, it remains one of the most widely published Lithuanian books to this day.

Question:

What was Adele's profession?

Answer:

- A. Lawyer
- B. Teacher**
- C. Doctor

Before going to the next location ask participants:

Can you say where is East? Travel along Gediminas Ave. to the east until you see a Children's playground in a small square. There is a woman looking at it, she is remembered only as a Lithuanian writer, forgetting her active social and political activities.

If participants do not know who it is, choose one group to lead everyone else along Gediminas Avenue to the east (towards Cathedral square) until they notice the playground.

2	Žemaitės sq.	Žemaitė Julija Beniuševičiūtė-Žymantienė (1845 - 1921)
<p>Text to say about this famous woman:</p> <p>Don't judge her by her serious look. Julija, also known as Žemaitė, was a free spirit who didn't care about societal norms and loved to dance. She started writing stories at 50, becoming a key figure in Lithuania's culture and politics, particularly advocating for the rights of peasant women. Julija also participated in the first Lithuanian Women's Congress in 1907, where she addressed the challenges faced by underprivileged women. Fun fact: Žemaitė is the only woman ever featured on Litas (used to be the national currency of Lithuania) banknotes, though they were replaced by coins just four years later.</p> <p>Question: Which group of women did Žemaitė support in her life and writings?</p> <p>Answer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Peasant women B. Women factory workers C. Elderly single women <p>Before going to the next location ask participants: Go to Vienuolio str. Go from South to North until you find an institution marked with Braille (for the blind).</p> <p><i>Participants can use maps to get to Vienuolio str. And then without maps by looking at facades should discover the sign of the museum.</i></p> <p><i>The fastest team that finds out which direction to follow (with google maps or without) can lead the entire group.</i></p>		
3	B. Grincevičiūtė Memorial Apartment – Museum (A. Vienuolio str. 12)	Beatričė Grincevičiūtė (1911 - 1988)
<p>Text to say about this famous woman:</p>		

In the early 20th century in Lithuania, people with disabilities were often seen as a burden or as dependent on society. It didn't matter if they had talent, worked hard or wanted to contribute. This is why Beatričė didn't like being called a "blind singer." However, that's exactly how she was introduced before her first concert. Still, her talent shone brightly - she became one of the most famous sopranos in Lithuanian opera and recorded over 1300 songs. Now, you're in front of her apartment turned museum. Here, you can discover not just her music but also the Braille language.

Link extra: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ko13T98-6iM&ab_channel=Muzikama%C5%BEiausiams

Question:

Listen to the song performed by Grincevičiūtė. Who treated the sick mosquito in the song?

Answer:

- A. Frogs
- B. Children
- C. Flies**

Before going to the next location ask participants:

Go to Gedimino Ave. no. 13. Find a memorial plaque that mentions three famous Lithuanian politicians of the interwar period. What kind of institution was in the building that stood in this place?

The fastest team that finds out which direction to follow (with google maps or without) can lead the entire group.

4	Gedimino Ave. no. 13	Felicija Bortkevičienė (1873 - 1945)
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Text to say about this famous woman:

This plaque tells us that the Lithuanian council used to operate in this building. Felicija Bortkevičienė served here as a senior secretary, but her role extended far beyond that. If we had to list all the political, cultural, and charitable organizations where she energetically organized or managed, we would be here for quite a while. Surprisingly, she never held any official political positions. Once, there was a consideration for her to become the Minister of Provision and Public Work, but some government members had reservations about a woman

holding this position, so she was not chosen. Later, Felicija was nominated for the presidency of Lithuania but received only one vote.

Question:

Felicija never became a president. However, in 2009 Lithuanians elected the first ever woman president. What is her name?

Answer:

- A. Vilija Blinkevičiūtė
- B. Kazimiera Prunskienė
- C. **Dalia Grybauskaitė**

Before going to the next location ask participants:

Find the square where the most famous Lithuanian song is honored, often sung during national holidays or sports Events.

Hint: there is a statue of a man in front of a tower-like structure. Look around. Can you see any statues around?

The fastest team that finds out which direction to follow (with google maps or without) can lead the entire group.

5	Kudirka square	Eliza Orzeszkowa (1841 - 1910)
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Text to say about famous woman:

Back when Vilnius was called Wilno, this square was named after a famous Polish writer, Eliza Orzeszkowa. She lived in the city for a while and ran a successful publishing business until the Russian authorities shut it down. In her writing, you can find many topics related to feminism, like women's education, independence, marriage, work, and the struggles of illegitimate children.

In 1905, she was nominated for the Nobel Prize in Literature but was later overlooked in favor of another male writer. Four years later she was nominated a second time but was overlooked again in favor of Selma Lagerlöf.

Question:

When was Eliza Orzeszkowa nominated for the Nobel Prize in Literature for the first time?

Answer:

- A. 1905
- B. 1900
- C. 1911

Before going to the next location ask participants:

From the monument to V. Kudirka, go along Gedimino Ave. east about 170 steps until you see the following windows:

Show the picture of the Window on google maps:

https://www.google.com/maps/place/Senoji+kibinin%C4%97/@54.6867118,25.2821148,3a,37.5y,190.7h,120.02t/data=!3m6!1e1!3m4!1sA0mRfMxQ-3OCtd0mVCPvQA!2e0!7i16384!8i8192!4m17!1m9!3m8!1s0x46dd9410578f3e19:0x187d7caefc316da5!2sTotori%C5%B3+q.+1,+Vilnius,+01103+Vilniaus+m.+sav.!3b1!8m2!3d54.6865507!4d25.2819593!10e5!16s%2Fq%2F11c2hprOrf!3m6!1s0x46dd950939085129:0xa80d93b08a5caf96!8m2!3d54.6868473!4d25.2819089!10e5!16s%2Fq%2F11q_gr046c?entry=ttu

The fastest team that finds out which direction to follow (with google maps or without) can lead the entire group.

The most comfortable place to stand is somewhere between Go9 and “+++” restaurant. However, keep in mind this corner is busy, so try to find a place, where you will not obstruct the entire sidewalk

6	On the opposite side of Gedimino avenue 12.	Alexandra Jurašaitytė - Vailokaitienė (1895 - 1957)
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Text to say about famous woman:

Look up, can you see those huge windows on the top floor of Gedimino Avenue 12? There used to be a photo studio there. And you know the most famous photo taken there. You've seen it hundreds of times by now. But have you ever wondered who was behind the camera? Her name was Aleksandra, and she, along with her mother, took over her father's photo studio after his passing in 1915. She also traveled extensively, documenting the lives of

Lithuanian peasants, orphans, famous politicians, and more. Don't forget to take a group photo here to celebrate Aleksandra!

Question:

How old was Aleksandra when she photographed the Council of Lithuania in this studio in 1917? She was born in 1895.

Estimate number answer option:

Answer:

22

Number Options can be from 16 to 35

Notes for the team leader/guide:

Participants should do simple math $1895 - 1917$

Finish	Depending on where you want to finish the tour	
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Notes for the team leader/guide:

To finish the tour, you can come back to Kudirka Square or go down Šv. Jurgio str. until you see more open space with stairs. Or GO9 shopping center and use it's space with benches (depending on the weather conditions) to share the experience and gather feedback.

Ask participants:

- Which of the women they found most interesting.
- Which women they already knew and who was unknown.
- Which stories surprised them the most.
- What was the hardest part of the tour?
- Which of the women they would like to learn more about.

Other questions which you might think of.

LEVEL 2: How to implement an exciting tour.

1. Add Interactive Elements to excursion tour:

Define the interactive elements that will be incorporated at the local tour, such as Q&A sessions, discussions, or activities, to keep participants engaged. Utilize the HERSTORY app, to enhance the interactive experience. Organize a dedicated event at the closing of the tour, emphasizing to the activity of a woman presented at the local map.

To make the tour more exciting, we suggest using mobile app **Action Bound** with 6 pre-selected objects that you can find in the table down below.

If there are no options to use this app, you can use a map <https://map.herstoryproject.eu/> and create a quiz for those same objects and use those same questions from the table down below.

In case of internet connection failure, we recommend to have printed versions of the questions so you could read them out loud as well as to show visual materials.

Participants should be informed beforehand that internet connection will be needed for the tour. They should also be encouraged to look for the tour points themselves, while getting hints from the tour leader where to go next.

Treasure hunt:

For the best experience, the **Action Bound app** should be used for these activities.

After selecting a city (e.g. Vilnius) from the list of maps at <https://map.herstoryproject.eu/>, click on **Treasure Hunt** and follow the instructions there using the Action Bound app.

City, Country: Vilnius, Lithuania		
Meeting point: Lukiškės square		
Number	Treasure Hunt Point	Content
1	Museum of Occupations and Freedom Fights	Text to say about this famous woman: Adelė was much like many other women who helped to shape Lithuania's first Republic. She worked in various youth and women's organizations, wrote articles, poetry, and organized seminars. Adele also taught German at a girls' school until her arrest by KGB in 1946 for "contra-revolutionary"

		<p>activities. Despite enduring eight months of torture in a secret KGB prison, her spirit remained unbroken. Even in Siberian gulags she continued teaching and supporting other women, emphasizing forgiveness over revenge. This message was captured in a small prayer book called "Mary, Save Us,". Translated into more than nine languages and distributed in hundreds of thousands of copies, it remains one of the most widely published Lithuanian books to this day.</p> <p>Question: What was Adele's profession?</p> <p>Answer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Layer B. Teacher C. Doctor
2	<p>Žemaitė square</p>	<p>Text to say about this famous woman:</p> <p>Don't judge her by her serious look. Julija, also known as Žemaitė, was a free spirit who didn't care about societal norms and loved to dance. She started writing stories at 50, becoming a key figure in Lithuania's culture and politics, particularly advocating for the rights of peasant women. Julija also participated in the first Lithuanian Women's Congress in 1907, where she addressed the challenges faced by underprivileged women. Fun fact: Žemaitė is the only woman ever featured on Litas banknotes, though they were replaced by coins just four years later.</p> <p>Question: Which group of women did Žemaitė support in her life and writings?</p> <p>Answer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Peasant women B. Women factory workers C. Elderly single women
3	<p>A. Vienuolio st. 12</p>	<p>Text to say about this famous woman:</p> <p>In the early 20th century in Lithuania, people with disabilities were often seen as a burden or as dependent on society. It didn't matter if they had talent, worked hard or wanted to contribute. This is why Beatričė didn't like being called a "blind singer." However, that's exactly how she was introduced before her first concert. Still, her talent shone brightly - she became one of the most famous sopranos in Lithuanian opera and</p>

		<p>recorded over 1300 songs. Now, you're in front of her apartment turned museum. Here, you can discover not just her music but also the Braille language.</p> <p>Link extra: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ko13T98-6iM</p> <p>Question:</p> <p>Listen to the song performed by Grincevičiūtė. Who treated the sick mosquito in the song?</p> <p>Answer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Frogs B. Children C. Flies
4	Gediminas ave. 13	<p>Text to say about this famous woman:</p> <p>This plaque tells us that the Lithuanian council used to operate in this building. Felicija Bortkevičienė served here as a senior secretary, but her role extended far beyond that. If we had to list all the political, cultural, and charitable organizations where she energetically organized or managed, we would be here for quite a while. Surprisingly, she never held any official political positions. Once, there was a consideration for her to become the Minister of Provision and Public Work, but some government members had reservations about a woman holding this position, so she was not chosen. Later, Felicija was nominated for the presidency of Lithuania but received only one vote.</p> <p>Question:</p> <p>Felicija never became a president. However, in 2009 Lithuanians elected first ever woman president. What is her name?</p> <p>Answer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Vilija Blinkevičiūtė B. Kazimiera Prunskienė C. Dalia Grybauskaitė

5	Kudirka square	<p>Text to say about famous woman:</p> <p>Back when Vilnius was called Wilno, this square was named after a famous Polish writer, Eliza Orzeszkowa. She lived in the city for a while and ran a successful publishing business until the Russian authorities shut it down. In her writing, you can find many topics related to feminism, like women's education, independence, marriage, work, and the struggles of illegitimate children.</p> <p>In 1905, she was nominated for the Nobel Prize in Literature but was later overlooked in favor of another male writer. Four years later she was nominated a second time but was overlooked again in favour of Selma Lagerlöf.</p> <p>Question:</p> <p>When was Eliza Orzeszkowa nominated for the Nobel Prize in Literature first time?</p> <p>Answer:</p> <p>A. 1905 B. 1900 C. 1911</p>
6	Gedimino ave. 12	<p>Text to say about famous woman:</p> <p>Look up, can you see those huge windows on the top floor of Gedimino Avenue 12? There used to be a photo studio there. And you know the most famous photo taken there. You've seen it hundreds of times by now. But have you ever wondered who was behind the camera? Her name was Aleksandra, and she, along with her mother, took over her father's photo studio after his passing in 1915. She also traveled extensively, documenting the lives of Lithuanian peasants, orphans, famous politicians, and more. Don't forget to take a group photo here to celebrate Aleksandra!</p> <p>Question:</p> <p>How old was Aleksandra when she photographed the Council of Lithuania in this studio in 1917? She was born in 1895.</p> <p>Estimate number answer option:</p>

		<p>Answer: 22</p> <p>Number Options can be from 16 to 35</p>
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In case if you want to prepare your own route – add some other objects of the map, we share descriptions and Treasure Hunt/Quizz options down below:

Treasure Hunt / Map Point	Content
Šermukšnių st. 1	<p><i>Text to say about famous woman:</i></p> <p>Lea Schemiavitz, known as Lili to her family, was just 10 years old when she was imprisoned in the Vilnius ghetto. What might she have grown up to be? Perhaps a teacher, a businesswoman, an artist, or a prime minister? Sadly, we will never know, as she perished near Bezdonys. All that's left are this stone and her brother's memories.</p> <p>Link Extra: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rH3U1U8wwd8&ab_channel=WorldJewishCongress</p> <p>Question: Why do some members of the Jewish community oppose the Stolperstein project?</p> <p>Answer:</p> <p>A. Because everyone is stepping on dead peoples' names and it is disrespectful.</p> <p>B. Because plaques are easily damaged</p> <p>C. Because no one notices them</p>
Jogailos st. 11	<p><i>Text to say about these famous women:</i></p> <p>Two little girls used to live in this building. One of them is mentioned on this memorial plaque. Despite the turmoil of World War II, Marija Gimbutienė managed to become a world-famous archaeologist and anthropologist. She made a groundbreaking</p>

	<p>discovery, revealing that 5000 years ago, Old European communities were woman-centered, practicing peace and equality. This new view of European history inspired countless scientists and feminist artists. Her cousin Meilė Lukšienė (1913-2009) on the other hand shaped your life - she played an important role in changing the school education system in Lithuania just after independence!</p> <p>Question: In which field did Marija Gimbutienė excelled?</p> <p>Hint: You have to finish doctoral studies to get this degree.</p> <p>Answer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. History B. Archeology C. Philology
<p>Vilniaus st. 25</p>	<p><i>Text to say about famous women:</i></p> <p>This building used to be a hospital founded by one of Lithuania's first female doctors, Veronika Janulaitytė - Alseikiene (1883–1971). Her sister, Dr. Julija Janulaitytė - Matjošaitiene (1880–1978), also worked here. Despite coming from a poor family, both sisters became doctors and did a lot of charity and cultural work outside their medical practice. They also raised their daughters, Marija and Meilė, who became influential scholars.</p> <p>Question: Find out which body part Veronika Alseikienė focused on healing. Doctors who specialize in this body part are called Ophthalmologists.</p> <p>Answer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Eyes B. Heart C. Teeth

<p>Labdarių st. 1-3</p>	<p>Text to say about famous woman:</p> <p>Did you know that the first secret service squad in Lithuania was composed entirely of women? The most courageous and determined among them was Marcelė Kubiliūtė. Some say that she held the entire safety of the young Lithuanian nation in her hands! In 1919, she played a crucial role in uncovering a secret plot to overthrow the Lithuanian government based in Kaunas at that time. The Polish secret service, annoyed by her interference, even put a 5000 zloty bounty on her, and she became known as the "woman with a fox." Can you guess why? Till this day she is the only Lithuanian woman awarded all major Lithuanian orders.</p> <p>Question: All spies in history had a nickname. If you had to go on a secret mission, what nickname would you choose?</p> <p>Answer: Your creativity 😊</p>
<p>Tilto st. 1</p>	<p>Text to say about famous woman:</p> <p>For a while, a young woman lived in this house. She became one of the most influential women in Lithuania between the two World Wars, and not just because she was married to the longest-serving Prime Minister. Jadvyga played a key role in founding the Lithuanian Women's Council. She was also a writer, journalist, and diplomat. Did you know she's the reason the Act of Independence of Lithuania became known worldwide? Jadvyga translated the Act into German and discreetly handed it to her friend, the editor of a significant newspaper. He took it to Berlin the next day and published it for the world to see!</p> <p>Question: Which important document did Jadvyga help make public and known worldwide risking her freedom in the process?</p> <p>Answer: A. the Act of Independence of Lithuania</p>

	<p>B. The document of founding Lithuanian Women's Council C. The Soviet–Lithuanian Peace Treaty</p>
<p>Pilies st. 26</p>	<p><i>Text to say about famous woman:</i></p> <p>Every year on February 16, we hold annual ceremonies to commemorate our independence at the House of the Signatories. Leaders of the country give speeches from the balcony, and hundreds of people fill the streets with flags, braving the cold February weather to celebrate freedom and independence. But who was this freedom for? At that time, hardly any country in the world recognized women as equal members of society with the right to vote or run for office. Lithuanian women were not satisfied with this. They raised their voices and won these rights. Today, they continue to raise their voices to gain more recognition for their historical contributions, one exhibition at a time...</p> <p>Question: Find out when Lithuania celebrate National Emancipation Day. Hint: It is celebrated next day after one of Lithuanian Independence days.</p> <p>Hint: It is celebrated next day after one of Lithuanian Independence days.</p> <p>Answer:</p> <p>A. February 17th</p> <p>B. March 8th</p> <p>C. April 16th</p>

2. Verify accessibility and provide necessary information:

Ensure that the tour is accessible to all, ensuring the equal experience to diverse audience, considering physical accessibility, language options, and cultural sensitivity. Use inclusive communication elements (language and visuals).

The Vilnius tour is prepared to be conducted in Lithuanian or English languages but if needed – you can translate the descriptions of your desired objects into your preferred language suitable for your group.

Accessibility for people with physical disabilities varies, but most often would require assistance from other people.

In this tour there are no planned visitations to any inside objects like museums. If you wish to visit them, please plan it ahead and check museums availability.

3. Receive Feedback and Improvement:

Collect feedback from participants to continually improve the tour experience. Stay updated on new monuments or developments related to women's history to keep the tour content current.

After the pilot excursion, we will invite the participants to sit down at Kudirka square and share their feedback, fill out the evaluation questionnaire.

At the end of the pilot excursion, participants will discuss their satisfaction and complete evaluation questionnaires. First, they'll fill out the HerStory evaluation form to help us improve future tours, followed by the European Union (EU) survey. Our team will also gather indicators of engagement and satisfaction. At the final stop of the treasure hunt, participants can share suggestions or concerns. In the following days, email reminders will be sent to those who haven't completed the EU survey.

4. Engage Locals through Collaborations:

Collaborate with local historians, institutes, experts, or community leaders who can provide insights into the historical and cultural context of each monument. Moreover, consider involving local women's groups or organizations in the planning and execution of the tour. Conduct research, to see if there are other events dedicated to women on the local monuments, that can be linked to the excursion tour.

Experts have contributed to identifying locations relevant to significant historical women, ensuring that the information we have collected is both historically accurate and pertinent to today's societal challenges. One of these experts is a professional guide with seven years of experience in leading tours for youth. She will be leading both the pilot and final tours.

LEVEL 3: Generic guidelines for individual and self-guided tours.

1. Enable the customization of excursions:

Ensure that the excursion is flexible to be tailored allowing participants to focus on specific themes or time periods related to women's history. Build on exclusive thematic, related to women's actions (e.g. national holidays, arts festivals, other national days). Consider organizing the tours around specific themes, such as historical periods, professions, or achievements, to add depth and structure.

Depending on the needs of participants, excursions can be customized according to a few different themes. For example, the Lithuanian national movement can be discussed by highlighting the works of women who were deeply involved in these processes. While focusing on this theme, it makes sense to organize the tours around national holidays like Independence Day. More broadly, tours can focus on culture and the arts. Many women mentioned in this tour wrote books and created art from a woman's perspective, which was often neglected by men. Moreover, another theme could be the struggle for women's rights in Lithuania in the 20th and 21st centuries. Tours could emphasize how many women worked to help the less privileged, addressed problems faced by women, and organized women's movements. If this theme is emphasized, it would make sense to schedule these tours around National Emancipation Days or International Women's Day.

2. Develop options for Training Guides or/and self-guided tours:

Involve tour guides that are well educated and conscious of the content and thematic of the excursion, to deliver accurate and engaging tour. In the case of self-guided tours, ensure the quality of information shared and the interactive element.

We recommend making the tour interactive by having the guide pose questions to participants, with correct answers leading to the next location. This treasure hunt approach encourages active participation and makes the learning experience more engaging and memorable.

Alternatively, the tour can be self-guided, allowing participants to explore at their own pace using a map or the Action Bound mobile app. Self-guided tours offer flexibility and independence, ideal for individual or small group exploration. Review and adapt the itinerary beforehand, and research the locations and notable women to fully appreciate their historical significance. Additional notes for the team leader can help teachers or youth workers with limited experience make this adaptation smoothly.

Extra tips

Having a QRCode printed to go to the local map of the city, so people can follow the tour or access the guidelines to make the tour in an educational way.

Application named Action Bound is recommended to use for full experience. It can be downloaded for free at Google Play or Apple Store.

<https://en.actionbound.com/>

Link to the map of women, where you can find all 12 tour points with their descriptions:

<https://map.herstoryproject.eu/vilnius/>

Link to the Transnational map of projects participants-cities:

<https://map.herstoryproject.eu/>

Link to the mandatory completion EU questionnaire for project participants:

https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/CERV_2021-2027

Link to the HerStory tour questionnaire where participants can leave their feedback:

<https://forms.office.com/pages/responsepage.aspx?id=DjZ60K5mRkCtIyoHZtHBgzH8XrcxF-JLp1B8xfR41k9UQlg3R0ZNNVE5VUo4ODEwRTdRRExSQkFOTy4u&route=shorturl>

2. Documentation and templates

The deliverables of WP4 activities are presented below:

- **D4.1 HERSTORY MAP pilot implementation**
- **Invitation/ agenda/ program:** A template will be shared by KEAN.
- **Signed attendance list**
- **Mintes/ report (tbd)**
- **Other evidence** (in case of pictures we need consent forms)